

ADOPTION AND MEANINGFUL USE OF SOCIAL MEDIA BY HEALTHCARE PROVIDERS IN RURAL HEALTH UNIT OF SOLANO, NUEVA VIZCAYA TO SHARE MEDICAL INFORMATION ON VACCINES

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ABSTRACT

Healthcare providers play a vital role in advancing public health by sharing accurate information, fostering trust, and promoting healthy behaviors within communities. In today's digital age, social media has emerged as a powerful platform for health communication, enabling professionals to disseminate information quickly, counter misinformation, and engage with wider and more diverse audiences beyond traditional methods. While many studies have examined the effectiveness of electronic health initiatives globally, there is a notable lack of research in the Philippine context, particularly in rural areas like the Rural Health Unit (RHU) of Solano, Nueva Vizcaya. This study explored how healthcare providers adopt and utilize social media for vaccine-related communication, focusing on their experiences, strategies, perceptions, and the barriers they face. Using a descriptive-qualitative design, data were gathered through interviews and focus group discussions with 25 purposively selected healthcare workers. The findings indicated that social media is considered an essential tool for community engagement and health education, especially in reaching various age groups and demographics. Effective strategies identified include consistent posting of relatable content, use of visuals, collaboration with local influencers, and active interaction with community members. However, challenges such as inadequate digital literacy, limited access to technology, unreliable internet connectivity, and the spread of misinformation were also observed. The study emphasizes the need for continuous digital skills training, stronger collaboration with barangay health workers, and the establishment of clear guidelines to ensure responsible and impactful social media use. Ultimately, the research emphasizes the potential of social media to enhance vaccine promotion and health communication in rural areas when applied thoughtfully and strategically.

Keywords: Healthcare provider, social media, vaccine hesitancy, thematic analysis

INTRODUCTION

Healthcare providers (HCPs) are recognized as key advocates and facilitators of immunization. Their recommendations have a significant positive influence on vaccination uptake, even among parents who harbor concerns about vaccine safety (Paterson et al., 2016). The confidence of HCPs in recommending vaccines is enhanced when they receive accurate information from reputable sources. However, logistical barriers such as time constraints can impede their advocacy efforts. Effective provider education, grounded in trustworthy information, is therefore critical for enabling HCPs to serve as reliable sources of vaccine information (Lin et al., 2021).

Rapid advancements in digital technologies have significantly transformed healthcare by shifting from manual processes to sophisticated digital solutions such as electronic health records, telemedicine, and artificial intelligence-enabled patient management (Edo et al., 2023). Advancements in mobile technology and increased internet accessibility have significantly driven the expansion of social media as a tool for health promotion (Stellefson et al., 2020). With billions of users worldwide, social media platforms support real-time information sharing, networking, and community building and have become influential in healthcare decision-making processes (Edington

et al., 2016). Unlike traditional media, content on social media does not undergo editorial curation or scientific vetting, resulting in the circulation of both empirical evidence and personal opinions. Such characteristics have played a notable role in shaping public attitudes and behaviors toward COVID-19 vaccines (Biswas et al., 2022). Recognizing this shift, the World Health Organization emphasizes the critical role of electronic health (eHealth) and social media in enhancing public health, particularly through facilitating personalized medicine and promoting equitable health policies worldwide (WHO, 2020). Moreover, social media companies and digital platforms are increasingly encouraged to apply global principles for identifying credible health information sources to combat misinformation and improve public trust (WHO, 2022). This collaborative approach aims to ensure that health information disseminated online is science-based, objective, transparent, and accountable, thereby supporting informed health decisions across diverse populations.

However, the unregulated nature of social media platforms has also contributed to the rapid spread of misinformation, leading to what has been termed an “infodemic” during events such as the COVID-19 pandemic (Clark et al., 2022). Social media, while promising to promote health equity among disadvantaged populations, has inconsistent empirical evidence on its effectiveness in improving public health outcomes. To optimize the potential of social media, it was crucial to effectively leverage these technological tools to create scalable, culturally adapted health promotion programs and campaigns (Welch et al., 2016).

Immunization is vital for ensuring every child’s fundamental right to holistic health. Unfortunately, routine immunization coverage among children in the Philippines has not reached the optimal target of 95%, with coverage rates for various vaccines declining from 2010 to 2021, as reported by the World Health Organization (2022). This decrease has led to outbreaks of measles and polio in 2019, which exposed children to the risks of these potentially life-threatening diseases (UNICEF, 2019). Subsequently, in early 2019, several regions in the Philippines experienced outbreaks of measles, resulting in over 33,000 cases that overwhelmed the capacities of numerous hospitals (DOH, 2019). In response to this crisis, a vaccination campaign was launched. However, according to the findings by Reyes et al. (2021), various challenges emerged during the vaccine administration process. Previous studies suggested that individuals’ perceptions of information, such as cognitive appraisals and judgments, were the main factors influencing behavioral intention. Although many studies have been conducted on the effectiveness of electronic health among patients and health workers, only a few studies regarding this matter were identified to have taken place in the Philippines, specifically in the Rural Health Unit of Solano. The study aimed to understand how healthcare providers in the Rural Health Unit of Solano utilized social media to share medical information on vaccines.

Statement of Objectives

This study sought to determine the extent to which the providers are currently utilizing social media platforms and to uncover the qualitative aspects of how healthcare providers engage with social media for vaccine-related communication. The study was conducted during the second semester of the year 2024-2025. Specifically, it aimed to provide answers to the following objectives:

1. To describe the impact of the healthcare providers’ social media engagement on health-related communication in terms of:
 - a. Preferences on the social media platforms they used;
 - b. Strategies in employing vaccine-related information;
 - c. Factors that enhance social media engagement;
 - d. Barriers that healthcare providers faced in adopting social media for vaccine

communication; and
e. Advantages of the use of social media for vaccine and medical information dissemination.

METHODOLOGY

The descriptive-qualitative approach was used in this study to analyze the healthcare providers' experiences and perceptions on the uptake and meaningful use of social media in distributing vaccine information. The research project focused on examining the use of social media platforms to disseminate information about vaccines, as perceived by healthcare professionals within the Rural Health Unit (RHU) of Solano. The participants, regardless of gender, consisted of twenty-five (25) healthcare workers from the Rural Health Unit of Solano. Two (2) Doctors, seven (7) nurses, ten (10) midwives, and six (6) Barangay Health Workers, ages 20-40, participated in the study. All participants were experienced in vaccine administration and were selected through a set of criteria in purposive sampling. This criterion encompasses (i) Healthcare workers currently employed in the Rural Health Unit of Solano, Nueva Vizcaya, (ii) Healthcare workers who are licensed to practice, (iii) Healthcare workers who are knowledgeable in vaccine administration, and (iv) Healthcare workers who utilize social media to share information.

Data were gathered through the use of a semi-structured interview guide questionnaire adopted from a study by McGowan et al. (2012) The research instrument includes the identified sources, namely: Current Use of social media, Frequency of Social Media Usage, Attitudes toward Social Media Usage, Usefulness of social media, Personal and Professional Innovativeness, Access to Peers, and Barriers to adopting social media for vaccine communication. The Thematic Analysis was conducted in six sequential stages: (1) familiarization with the data, (2) generation of initial codes, (3) identification of potential themes, (4) review and refinement of themes, (5) identification and definition of themes, and (6) comprehensive thematic report.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Section 1: Social Media Platforms Used for Dissemination

The majority of participants indicated that Facebook is the primary platform they use to disseminate vaccination information. They emphasized that Facebook allows for easy sharing of content and enables them to reach a broad audience. Specifically, respondents mentioned that by using features such as Facebook pages, they are able to effectively relay medical information to a wide and diverse group of users.

Theme 1: Platform Preference and Accessibility

Platform preference refers to the tendency of individuals or organizations to choose specific social media apps, such as Facebook, Twitter, or Instagram, for disseminating medical information based on factors like audience reach, ease of use, and perceived credibility. Accessibility describes how easily diverse users, including those with disabilities or language barriers, can access, understand, and engage with medical information shared on these platforms. Together, platform preference and accessibility influence the effectiveness of social media in spreading reliable health information, ensuring that it reaches and benefits the widest possible audience.

Individuals utilize traditional and online media platforms for diverse reasons and objectives, influenced by personal preferences and the abundance of available informational and entertainment

sources (Daramola, 2003). This study was further supported with the following verbatims; “Facebook ang ginagamit talaga pero sa ibang social media apps, wala masyado. Talagang facebook lang talaga.” (Facebook is commonly utilized but for other social media apps, it is used rarely. Facebook is utilized.), “Ang common na ginagamit ko is facebook. Yun lang naman. Instagram, gumagamit din naman pero mas nagagamit talaga yung facebook” (I use facebook commonly. That is all. For instagram, I also use it, but I use facebook more.), “Personally, I use facebook and reddit.” (Personally, ginagamit ko si Facebook, tapos Reddit.)

Martinez et al. (2018) demonstrated that the widespread accessibility and adoption of social networking platforms make them effective tools for health promotion and preventive interventions. These platforms facilitate efficient outreach to large and diverse audiences, surpassing traditional methods. Healthcare providers should utilize the accessibility and widespread adoption of platforms such as Facebook to disseminate vital health information. However, ensuring accessibility for diverse populations, including those with disabilities or language barriers, is crucial to maximizing the impact of these communication strategies.

Theme 2: Functionality and Usability

Functionality and usability in utilizing social media apps for disseminating medical information refer to how well these platforms support users in effectively accessing, sharing, and interacting with health content. Functionality encompasses the specific features and tools social media apps provide, such as posting, commenting, multimedia sharing, live streaming, and notifications, that enable health professionals and organizations to communicate medical information efficiently. Usability relates to the ease with which diverse users, including patients and healthcare providers, can navigate these platforms, understand the content, and engage in meaningful dialogue without technical difficulties or barriers. High functionality combined with good usability ensures that medical information is not only delivered but also comprehended and acted upon, enhancing health communication outcomes and user satisfaction across different populations.

In the study of Limaye et al. (2021), social media exerts a significant influence on vaccine acceptance, primarily through the strategic framing of messages, the selection of credible messengers, and the structure of online networks playing pivotal roles in shaping public attitudes. One participant shared, “I use Facebook for updates or if there is advocacy and advisory that needs to be announced, and has to be reached to the people, and it is accessible for the people since we have pages such as the RHU Health Education and Promotion.” (Ginagamit ko yung sa Facebook for updates or if may advocacy at advisory kami na kailangan maipaabot sa mga tao, tapos mas accessible sa mga tao kasi may mga pages kami tulad ng RHU Health Education and Promotion.)

The functionality and usability of social media platforms are essential for healthcare professionals to disseminate medical information effectively. For nurses, utilizing these platform capabilities supports the rapid sharing of accurate health information and fosters community trust. As social media increasingly influences public health, optimizing its functionality and usability empowers nurses to be trusted sources, improve vaccine acceptance, and promote healthier communities.

Section 2: Strategies and Techniques for Dissemination

The participants primarily disseminated vaccine-related and medical information through group chats on Messenger and announcements posted on Facebook pages. In addition to these platforms, other communication channels such as posters, flyers, and phone calls are also employed

for information dissemination. Furthermore, to ensure that the information effectively reaches the community, Barangay Health Workers conduct house-to-house visits as part of their outreach efforts. The interview findings brought two key themes: Targeted Messaging and Community Engagement, and Multi-Channel Approach.

Theme 1: Targeted Messaging and Community Engagement

This theme combines two important concepts: Targeted messaging involves creating and delivering personalized content design for specific audience segments based on shared traits such as demographics and interests, ensuring the message is relevant, engaging, and effective. Community engagement, on the other hand, is a strategic process that actively involves local populations in communication and collaboration to build trust, encourage participation, and achieve mutually beneficial results. This approach involves tailoring messages to specific audiences based on cultural, social, or individual characteristics. Shen et al. (2023) emphasized the critical role of trusted messengers and community-based organizations in delivering targeted messages about COVID-19 and routine immunizations.

Other research supports that community engagement improves vaccine uptake and reduces the burden of vaccine-preventable diseases. Dutta et al. (2021) underscore that in the context of India, effective community engagement is facilitated through trusted local influencers and the dissemination of social-behavioral change communication. Community engagement promotes culturally sensitive dialogue that can reduce the refusal rate and improve access to vaccination services, thereby addressing both informational and access barriers effectively. Effective strategies include targeted messaging, health education, and social mobilization (Bedford et al., 2017).

Community engagement interventions such as stakeholder consultations and involvement of community leaders have shown effectiveness in improving routine childhood immunization outcomes in low and middle-income countries (Jain et al., 2022). The role of nurses extends beyond clinical settings as they act as trusted mediators between healthcare systems and communities. By providing health education, screenings, and support directly within community venues such as homes or schools, nurses improve accessibility and address social determinants of health.

Theme 2: Multi-Channel Approach

This theme encompasses the use of diverse communication platforms and media to distribute vaccine-related information effectively. It includes leveraging digital tools such as social media (e.g., Facebook, Messenger), internet sources, and traditional media like posters, flyers, and phone calls, ensuring wider reach and accessibility across different community preferences and access levels.

Research consistently demonstrates that employing a multi-channel approach to vaccine communication significantly enhances vaccine uptake and coverage. Integrating digital platforms such as social media, text messaging, and websites with traditional media outlets like television, newspapers, flyers, and posters ensures messages reach a wide and diverse audience (Hopfer et al., 2021). Although social media can sometimes spread misinformation, it remains a crucial tool for educating vaccine-hesitant individuals when combined with trusted community partners who respect audience preferences such as privacy and avoiding information overload (Hopfer et al., 2021).

Social media has gained prominence in healthcare as a tool for knowledge sharing and professional development. Research indicates that a significant majority of health researchers and

clinicians utilize social media for professional purposes, with 80% engaging in work-related activities on these platforms (Tununecliff et al., 2015). Clinicians frequently use platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, and WhatsApp to share clinical knowledge, with WhatsApp being particularly favored among healthcare professionals (Asfaw & Mekonnen, 2021). Furthermore, many physicians report that social media enhances patient care and contributes to improved care quality (McGowan et al., 2012)

Nurses are instrumental in delivering timely, personalized reminders and educational messages that address individual concerns and overcome barriers such as misinformation and limited healthcare access, thereby promoting vaccine acceptance and adherence. Collaboration with community health workers and local leaders enables the dissemination of consistent, culturally appropriate messages tailored to the unique needs of specific communities.

Section 3: Factors Enhancing Social Media Engagement

The factors that enhanced social media engagement were the usage of the local language, Tagalog, so that the target audience could understand the announcements. They further explained that only important information was posted to prevent lengthy and boring announcements, which others might skip reading. Another factor was sharing it on Facebook and posting it in public, either using private accounts or after the approval of the municipality to share it via the official Facebook page of the Rural Health Unit of Solano. This collection of answers formed three themes, namely, content attractiveness, interactivity and responsiveness, and clarity and credibility.

Theme 1: Language Use

It encompasses the multifaceted ways in which individuals employ language to communicate, encompassing both spoken and written modalities. This demonstrates that content attractiveness through language inclusivity, cultural relevance, and clarity is key to capturing attention, enhancing engagement, and effectively disseminating vaccine information on Facebook among diverse Filipino communities. This was demonstrated through a verbatim "Ang pinaka cinoconsider talaga minsan, 'yung paggamit ng language na maiintindihan talaga nila. Considering na 'yung mga tao naman na pupuntahan ng information, e diverse, kailangan common language 'yung gagamitin, pwedeng tagalog or iloko." (What we really consider most of the time is using a language that people can truly understand. Since the people who will receive the information are diverse, we need to use a common language, which can be Tagalog or Ilocano.)

Nurses play a crucial role in vaccine education by using language and cultural sensitivity to communicate with Filipino communities effectively. By delivering vaccine information in Tagalog, Ilocano, and English with clear, relatable messages and culturally appropriate visuals, nurses can build trust and encourage vaccine acceptance, especially among mothers and rural populations. This culturally responsive approach enhances patient understanding, promotes informed decision-making, and supports public health efforts to increase vaccination rates in diverse Filipino communities.

Theme 2: Interactivity and Responsiveness

It refers to the back-and-forth connection between content creators and their audience, especially on social media. Interactivity means making content that encourages people to join in and take part instead of just watching or reading quietly. Responsiveness is about how quickly and thoughtfully creators or healthcare providers respond when people engage- whether it's answering

questions, giving feedback, clearing up confusion, or sparking conversations right away. It's this kind of real-time exchange that makes the experience more personal and meaningful for everyone involved.

Patient networks like PatientsLikeMe can make patients communicate with one another and exchange health-related information and guidance, such as data on medication and treatment. Social media platforms that allow real-time conversations between health professionals and the public also play a vital role in building trust and reducing vaccine hesitancy, as timely and active engagement helps combat misinformation and establishes credibility (Marzo et al., 2022). Nurses are key contributors in encouraging vaccine acceptance by engaging openly and responsively with patients and communities, especially through social media platforms that allow two-way conversations. When nurses listen to concerns, answer questions promptly, and provide clear, trustworthy information in a respectful and culturally sensitive way, they help build confidence in vaccines and reduce fears fueled by misinformation.

Theme 3: Clarity and Credibility

It refers to delivering a simple, easy-to-understand message that truly connects with the audience, avoiding confusion and building trust. Credibility is about being trustworthy and consistent, showing accuracy, and staying true to the values of the Department of Health and the Rural Health Unit of Solano. Together, they ensure the message reaches the right people, resonates with them, and encourages meaningful engagement.

The use of local languages such as Tagalog and Ilocano enhances comprehension and trust, while the involvement of health professionals as credible sources further strengthens message reliability (Berdida et al., 2021; PLOS Global Public Health, 2022). Additionally, the practice of requiring posts to be approved by local government units ensures that information is accurate and consistent with public health policies, which is crucial in building public confidence and preventing the spread of conflicting messages (PLOS Global Public Health, 2022). This approach aligns with recommendations to engage communities using culturally appropriate, clear, and credible communication to improve vaccine uptake in diverse Filipino populations.

Nurses must provide clear and trustworthy vaccine information in languages that Filipino patients understand, such as Tagalog and Ilocano, to help overcome misinformation and vaccine hesitancy. Being credible sources of information, nurses should communicate openly and confidently about vaccine safety and benefits to build trust.

Section 4: Advantages of Posting Vaccine Information on Social Media

Interview feedback revealed that social media's main benefits were its accessibility, wide reach, and enhanced patient-healthcare interaction. The ideas identified in the responses were categorized into two themes: Increased awareness and uptake, and community feedback and support.

Theme 1: Increased Awareness and Uptake

It refers to the measurable growth in participants' knowledge and use of social media for sharing medical information. Through social media, patients can join virtual communities, participate in research, receive financial or moral support, set goals, and track personal progress (Lambert et al., 2012). The findings indicate that social media's growing role in sharing health information offers

great potential but also presents some risks for nurses and future nurses. By carefully understanding the advantages and disadvantages and having effective guidelines and training, nurses can use social media to improve patient care, boost professional skills, and strengthen the nursing profession.

Theme 2: Community Feedback and Support

This theme focuses on the observable interactions between healthcare workers and patients within the online community. This includes direct feedback through comments, replies, likes, and shares. At the same time, support is defined as the acts of assistance given by the healthcare workers to the patients that include informational support, such as clarifying information for the patients and addressing queries regarding medical information, and practical support, which encompasses problem-solving techniques that are disseminated through infographics and poster templates.

Scanfeld et al. (2010) highlighted the pivotal role of social media in public health communication, noting its capacity to monitor public responses to health issues, track disease outbreaks, identify misinformation, and disseminate accurate information to targeted communities. These functions enhance the effectiveness of communication strategies by providing timely insights into public perception and engagement. Positive feedback reinforces message credibility, while community interaction fosters trust and broadens the dissemination of health information.

Section 5: Disadvantages and Challenges of Posting Vaccine Information

A significant number of challenges encountered in posting vaccine information on social media stemmed from misinformation and negative reactions circulating within the community.

Theme 1: Misinformation

A recurring concern in the responses is the widespread presence of misinformation on social media. Respondents pointed out that misinformation or misleading information about vaccines spread quickly and influenced the community's perception. The unregulated nature of social media platforms makes it difficult to control the spread of false information, and users may find it challenging to distinguish credible sources from unreliable ones.

Misinformation, including the idea that vaccines are harmful or part of sinister conspiracies, has proliferated and amplified public skepticism (Larson et al., 2022). Research into Filipino vaccine-hesitant social media users revealed that COVID-19 vaccine hesitancy was shaped in large part by disinformation and misinformation defined by misbeliefs and lacking adequate knowledge (Berdinda et al., 2022). In addition, misinformation has caused hesitancy across specific brands in the Philippines. Individuals feel distrustful of some vaccines based on social media-driven speculation and a lack of transparency (Amit et al., 2022; Mendoza et al., 2021). Such outcomes highlight the need for immediate action in coordinated efforts from government institutions, healthcare providers, and educational institutions to address misinformation and enforce accurate, culture-sensitive health communication on social media platforms (Hernandez et al., 2021). Hence, nurses need to practice proactive communication by presenting straightforward, evidence-based information addressing false claims in order to instill trust and encourage vaccine uptake.

Theme 2: Negative Reactions

Participants noted that discussions about vaccines often become contentious and emotionally charged. Such negative responses comprise distrust based on rumors, religious or cultural

opposition, and rejection of information because of "overthinking" from repeated exposure to conflicting messages. One participant shared "May mga parents an ayaw ipabakuna yung anak, lalo na yung mga religious yung mga may pinapaniwalaan yung mga ibang sect. Meron talagang hindi nagpapabakuna. Yung mga Jehova's witness, hindi sila nagpapabakuna." (Some parents refuse to have their children vaccinated, especially those who are religious or belong to certain sectors. There are really some who don't get vaccinated. For example, Jehovah's Witnesses—they don't get vaccines most of the time.)

Research has recorded how social media facilitates anti-vaccine views and conspiracy theories and how these facilitate an environment in which misinformation easily spreads and emotional responses discourage meaningful discussion (Basch et al., 2021; Scannell et al., 2021). In the Philippines, disinformation about vaccines on Facebook and other media has been attributed to declining child immunization and vaccine-preventable disease outbreaks, as incorrect information and fear-mongering narratives deter vaccination (France 24, 2020; Patriarca, 2020).

Negative feedback, doubt, and disinformation can foster an antagonistic environment that dissuades open discussion and promotes vaccine hesitancy among the public. Nurses, being reputed healthcare providers, play a crucial role in responding to such reactions by engaging in accurate, compassionate, and culturally responsive communication to dispel disinformation and establish vaccine confidence. Evidence suggests that nurses' active presence on social media and in hospitals through education, conversation, and tailored advice reduces the effect of adverse reactions and encourages the uptake of vaccination.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The widespread reliance on Facebook as the primary social media platform for the dissemination of vaccination information to the Rural Health Unit highlights its accessibility, rapid reach, and strong user preference within the community. The platform's intuitive functionality, including dedicated pages and real-time updates, enables healthcare providers to efficiently share advocacy, advisories, and educational content with diverse audiences, even those in geographically dispersed barangays. Such usability not only streamlines communication but also ensures that important health messages are both received and understood by the target population.

The community vaccination program effectively leverages a multi-faceted approach to disseminate vital information about vaccines, particularly for infants and high-risk populations. Through various communication channels, including group chats, Messenger, and social media platforms, health workers maintain consistent engagement with the community, ensuring that essential messages regarding vaccination completion are conveyed. The collaboration between the Department of Health (DOH), Rural Health Units (RHU), midwives, and Barangay Health Workers enhances the outreach efforts, facilitating house-to-house visits and the distribution of educational materials.

The predominant use of Tagalog and Ilocano ensures that health information is comprehensible to the majority, fostering better understanding among diverse audiences. By prioritizing concise and straightforward messaging, the program not only enhances comprehension but also encourages engagement. The integration of social media as a tool for outreach allows for meaningful connections, facilitating conversations that build trust within the community. Additionally, employing visually engaging content, actively responding to followers, and collaborating with local leaders and influencers further enhances the impact of health communications.

Utilizing social media platforms, particularly Facebook, has significantly enhanced both awareness and uptake of vaccination programs by enabling rapid, wide-reaching, and interactive communication between the Rural Health Unit and the community. The accessibility of these platforms allows health workers to efficiently disseminate reminders and vital information to a broad audience with minimal effort, eliminating the need for time-consuming house-to-house visits.

Misinformation and disinformation pose significant challenges to public health initiatives, particularly in the context of vaccination programs. This phenomenon is exacerbated by fear and distrust surrounding vaccines, often fueled by anecdotal experiences and opinionated narratives. Certain groups, such as those with specific religious beliefs, may further resist vaccination efforts, complicating outreach and education strategies. Addressing these challenges requires proactive measures, including enhancing the clarity and credibility of health communications, engaging with the community to dispel myths, and fostering open dialogues to build trust.

Recommendations

Healthcare providers should have a background on other social media platforms so that they can share information with people of various age groups, since community members use different social media platforms. Younger individuals use platforms aside from Facebook and Messenger. They should increase their use of social media to obtain knowledge and insights on health issues so that they can share more accurate information with the community. Since not all people have access to the Internet and social media, they should conduct regular face-to-face information dissemination activities and strengthen their collaboration with barangay health workers.

The Rural Health Unit should also conduct digital literacy training to ensure that healthcare providers have a background on the different platforms used for disseminating vaccine-related information, and this should be geared especially toward those who do not plan to use or adopt other social media platforms. There should also be IT specialists who will assist healthcare providers in sharing and creating vaccine-related information. There should be a regular evaluation of the effectiveness of social media adoption on the vaccination program. The community should also give their feedback on the effectiveness of social media on the vaccination program and how it benefits them. Since one of the barriers to the adoption of social media and vaccination is vaccine hesitancy, they should participate in assemblies and seminars that aim to address myths and misconceptions about vaccines. They should also address the barriers that they experience with the use of social media in accessing vaccine-related information.

Lastly, future researchers should conduct a quantitative study on the effectiveness of social media in sharing vaccine-related information, and feedback from the community should be included.

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